

Extreme Value Analysis of the Rhône River Peak Flows in the Cantons of Valais and Vaud.

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Submission Date: 30.06.2025

Abstract

This thesis reassesses extreme flood events on the Rhône River in the Swiss cantons of Valais and Vaud by applying Extreme Value Analysis to updated discharge datasets. It aims to provide new estimates for T-year return period floods and to compare them to existing estimates, especially design values for the 3rd Rhône Correction flood protection project.

The analysis was conducted using several data scenarios, including the use of all available data, a natural conditions scenario based on pre-dam data and historical flood reconstructions, and a scenario focusing on 1995 to 2024. Estimates of the 100-year flood (Q100) under natural conditions confirm that discharges would likely be higher without the mitigating effect of reservoirs. Notably, estimates for Q100 in the recent period are significantly larger – partly due to the major flood event of June 2024. This points to a possible shift in the flood-generating processes of the region, in line with climate change projections.

The findings indicate that the design values (Q100cible) for the 3rd Rhône River correction are not oversized and may even be underestimated at Brig and Reckingen. A supplementary flood process analysis reveals that while various runoff mechanisms contribute to the overall flood distribution, the most severe peak discharges are disproportionately driven by extreme rainfall events.

These updated estimates emphasise the necessity of flood protection and provide new flood estimates for ongoing risk management in the Rhône valley. However, due to the limited length of the discharge time series, it would be suggested to further investigate with a modelling approach (a stochastic weather generation and a rainfall runoff model), to obtain more accurate flood estimates.

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List of Abbreviations

BLOCK	Block Maxima (approach)
CCA	Canonical-Correlation Analysis (also canonical variates analysis)
c.i.	confidence interval
E-AS SA	Eller & Associés Société Anonyme
EPE	Extreme Precipitation Event
EVA	Extreme Value Analysis
FOWG	Federal Office for Water and Geology
GEV	Generalized Extreme Value (distribution function)
GP	Generalized Pareto (distribution function)
IID	Independent and Identically Distributed
MLE	Maximum Likelihood Estimation
MRL	Mean Residual Life (plot)
PA-R3	Plan d'Aménagement (of the 3rd Rhône River Correction), German: GP-R3
POT	Peak over Threshold (method)
Q100	Discharge value [m ³ /s], which is exceeded with a probability of $\frac{1}{100}$ every year.
Q _{max}	The highest discharge, which was observed for a certain location
R3	3rd Rhône River Correction
TC	Threshold Choice (plot)

1 Introduction

In the past, there have been big floods in the Rhône river, which led to the first (1863-1894) and second (1930-1960) Rhône river correction (Vischer, 2003). Despite these interventions, there have been floods in the years 1987, 1993 and 2000 causing substantial economic damages (Voyame, 2024). The flood of 2000 prompted the development of the 3rd Rhône River Correction (R3), a flood protection project commissioned by the Grand Council of the Canton of Valais (Woolsey and Moosmann, 2004). Launched in 2000, the project was initially scheduled for completion by 2030, with an estimated cost of approximately 900 million francs (Woolsey and Moosmann, 2004). The goals of the R3 were the improvement of the security along the Rhône River, an ecological upgrading and a valorisation for the people. The R3 is an extensive flood protection project which is appendant to the Rhône from Gletsch to the river mouth at the lake Geneva (Canton of Valais, 2024).

For the dimensioning of a river correction project the estimations of flood discharge values with a T-year return period are considered important. The report CONSECRU 2 (Higray *et al.*, 2006) estimated these values for various discharge measurement stations along the Rhône River in the Cantons of Valais and Vaud. The analysis employed a simulation-based approach, the upper value of the 80% confidence interval (c.i.) and reconstructions of past historical floods to estimate the T-year return values under natural conditions. Natural means excluding retentional effects of dams in the catchment area. The results were relevant for the dimensioning of the R3, as it has been stated in the Plan d'Aménagement (PA-R3) (Canton of Valais and Canton of Vaud, 2016).

The Council of State of the Canton of Valais mandated a new report from Eller & Associés SA (E-AS SA), completed by C. Voyame in 2024. The report argues that the current flood estimates employed for the R3 – derived by neglecting reservoir retention, excluding effects of climate change and using the upper 80% c.i. – are oversized. The report suggests reevaluating the R3, because the current dimensioning leads to excessive costs and land use conflicts. However, experts criticized some of the arguments given in the report. In an interview (Morel, Stüssi and Speerli, 2024), Jürg Speerli stated that climate change would likely increase flood estimates rather than reduce them. He also noted that reservoir retention has a limited impact on flood mitigation in most Rhône catchment areas. Since major floods typically occur in late autumn – when reservoirs are already full – their capacity to hold back additional water is limited. Moreover, he emphasized that more precise weather forecasts would be necessary to implement preemptive water level reductions in the reservoirs.

In February 2024, the Council of State of the Canton of Valais has decided to revise the R3 and its General Project (PA-R3) by updating key flood protection data, reassessing technical decisions, and integrating new approaches to risk management, climate change, and territorial constraints (Council of State of the Canton of Valais, 2024). The decision to reevaluate the dimension of the project has been criticized in the media, because it will delay the execution of the R3, a project that was being planned

for over twenty years. Concerns amplified by the severe June 2024 flood (for example in the NZZ: Humbel, 2024). The flood caused significant infrastructure damage, including impacts on the aluminium industry, and displaced 140 residents in Sierre and Chippis (Bonamoni, 2024).

In comparison to flood estimations that have already been done, there is more available data to estimate now, because 18 years have passed since the CONSECRU 2 report (Higray *et al.*, 2006). New estimations could be particularly interesting because of the intensive flood in June 2024. Climate change projections indicate several key hydrological shifts: more intense precipitation events, an increased rainfall-to-snowfall ratio, and earlier spring snowmelt (FOEN, 2021; Brönnimann *et al.*, 2018). These factors are probably relevant for the Rhône River flood dynamics. The 2000 flood, for instance, was mitigated by multiple 100 m³/s due to snowfall in the catchment area at high altitudes above 3'000 m a.s.l. (Federal Office for Water and Geology (FOWG), 2002). The autumn 2023 flood was mild in the Valais, likely due to the limited snow availability that reduced snowmelt during the rain-on-snow event (BAFU, 2024b). In contrast, it was severe along the Arve River in the Canton of Geneva (Monbaron-Jalade *et al.*, 2024). Rain-on-snow played a significant role for the 2024 flood in the Valais (BAFU, 2025c). The new data will allow flood estimations under a warmer climate, accounting for some hydrological changes.

This bachelor's thesis conducts an extreme value analysis (EVA) of Rhône River discharge data across different measurement stations and for different data scenarios. EVA quantifies flood magnitudes associated with specific return periods. Often the Q50, Q100 and Q1000 return values are of interest in hydrological EVA (Reiss, 2007). For the comparison in the results the focus lies on the Q100. The newly calculated Q100 values will then be compared to existing estimations from FOWG in 2002, from the CONSECRU 2 report (Higray *et al.*, 2006) and from the flood statistics of the BAFU from 2020. Brief descriptions of the methodology and time periods, used to calculate these estimates, will be given in section 3.

This leads to the Research Question: *How do return values with a T-year return period of the Rhône River discharge vary across measurement stations and data scenarios, and how do they compare to prior analyses?*

Three data scenarios will be examined:

- Estimations with all available data
- Estimations for the natural situation, thus neglecting the retentional effect of reservoirs.
- Estimations for the more recent time period (1995-2024)

Hypothesis: Q100 estimates for natural conditions and the more recent time period will exceed those derived from the full dataset, due to climate change and reduced reservoir mitigation.

The estimations are calculated via the block maxima approach (BLOCK) and/or the Peak over Threshold (POT) method (see section 3). For the natural condition, a regression model is applied.

Additionally, a brief flood process analysis is given. Such analysis is important for flood protection, as it enhances early warning systems by identifying the key processes driving flood events (Merz *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, it improves flood estimation under climate change, by establishing relationships between well-researched climatic variables and flood generation processes (Merz *et al.*, 2014).

This analysis utilizes rainfall data to generate a rain index via Canonical Correlation Analysis (CCA), which correlates rainfall data with discharge data. Extreme Precipitation Events (EPEs) are defined through an EVA of the rain index and then matched with the declustered peak exceedances of the discharge. This approach aims to determine whether EPEs dominate the tail of the discharge distribution and whether their distribution within the tail is uniform. The working hypothesis, supported by Macdonald *et al.* (2024), suggests that the heavy weighted tail is generally controlled by extreme runoff generation events, with EPEs getting increasingly influential at higher return periods.

The primary objective of this bachelor's thesis is to give new estimates of T-year return period discharge values for the Rhône River in the Cantons of Valais and Vaud. New estimates could contribute to a proper dimensioning of flood protectional infrastructure, ultimately helping to safeguard infrastructure and communities throughout the Rhône valley.

2 Investigation Area and Data

The investigation area covers the Rhône Valley in the Cantons of Valais and Vaud from the source of the Rhône River until the outlet into Lake Geneva. The size of the total catchment area is 5'238 [km²], ranging in elevation from 371 to 4'521 [m a.s.l.], with an average elevation of 2124 [m a.s.l.] and an average slope of 26° (HADES, 2025). The dominant land cover types are rocky surfaces (24%), forests (23%), and grass and herbaceous vegetation (19%) (HADES, 2025). Glaciers currently cover 13% of the catchment, while 3% is occupied by settlements (HADES, 2025). Most of the settlement area is located along the main Rhône Valley and is projected to expand further in the coming years (Perlik *et al.*, 2008), thereby increasing the region's exposure to flooding.

For the analysis, discharge data [m³/s] from seven measurement locations were used. Table 1 provides an overview of the locations, the station IDs, the data availability and selected catchment characteristics. The locations are mapped in Figure 3.

Table 1: Overview of the discharge datasets. The altitude and area information's are from HADES (2025). There are two different station numbers for Brig and Reckingen due to slight relocations of the measurement sites over time. Specifically, the Brig station was located upstream of the Salina confluence prior to 1965. Data: BAFU (2025a) and Kauzlaric et al. (2025).

Location	Station Number	Time Period:	Time Period:	Mean altitude of the catchment area [m a.s.l.]	Area [km ²]	Glaciers [%]
		Annual Maxima [m ³ /s]	Hourly Discharge [m ³ /s]			
Porte du Scex	2009	1905-2024	1974-2024	2193	5220	13
Branson	2024	1941-2024	1974-2024	2264	3728	16
Sion	2011	1916-2024	1974-2024	2335	3349	17
Brig	2049 / 2346	1916-2024	1974-2024	2339	909.1	24
Reckingen	2419 / 2237	1950-2024	1975-2024	2306	217.3	16
Gletsch	2268	1956-2024	1974-1024	2712	40.70	52
Visp (Vispa)	2351	1974-2024	1974-2024	2655	789.6	27

The additional information on mean altitude and glaciation allows the classification of hydrological regimes for the catchment areas of the measurement stations, based on the scheme outlined by the BAFU (2024). According to this classification, Gletsch has an a-glacial regime, while Brig and Visp exhibit b-glacial regimes. The remaining stations - Porte du Scex, Branson, Sion and Reckingen - are characterized

by a glacio-nival regimes. These assignments are supported by annual discharge patterns, as illustrated in Figure 2 for the example of Porte du Scex.

Figure 2: Annual course of the mean daily discharge from 1974 to 2024 in Porte du Scex. Data: Kauzlaric et al. (2025)

However, the Rhône River from Brig to its outlet at Lake Geneva, as well as the Vispa in Visp, generally exhibit perturbed regimes due to human influences. As a result, standard regimes are typically not provided for these areas (e.g., swisstopo, 2000).

There is a total water store capacity of 1'200 million [m³] due to water retaining structures in the catchment area (Swiss Committee on Dams, 2015). Most of the dams were constructed between 1951 and 1975. Due to the location of these structures the locations Gletsch, Reckingen and Brig in the upper Valais are barely influenced by dams (FOWG, 2002). In total, around one-quarter of the catchment area is capped by water retaining structures (FOWG, 2002). The flood-mitigating effect of these structures is particularly significant for small, affected catchments like the Vispa in Zermatt (Morel, Stüssi and Speerli, 2024).

Measurement Stations

Figure 3: Measurement Stations in the Cantons of Valais and Vaud. Violet points indicate the locations of the water level measurement stations. Green points represent the selected manual precipitation measurement sites, while red points show manual stations that were not selected. The coordinates are from Kauzlaric et al. (2025) and MeteoSwiss (2025).

For the flood process analysis, daily manual rainfall measurements [mm] for fifteen locations in the Cantons of Valais and Vaud were used. Not all available stations were selected; some were excluded due to their location outside the relevant discharge catchment area or due to insufficient temporal data coverage. The data from automatic measurement stations was not included due to insufficient time coverage for a consistent analysis. Since no rainfall data within the catchment areas of Gletsch, Reckingen and Brig was used, these locations were excluded from the flood process analysis.

3 Methods

3.1 Extreme Value Analysis (EVA)

Accurate dimensioning of flood protection infrastructure requires estimates of rare and extreme hydrological events, including those that may not yet have been observed. EVA offers a statistical framework to extrapolate from observed extremes to unobserved extremes using an asymptotic argument (Bousquet, 2021). Many time series of streamflow and precipitation show heavy tailed distributions, meaning their upper tail decreases slower than normal (El Adlouni, Bobée and Ouarda, 2008). A range of statistical distribution functions can be used to model the distribution of the extreme values (Gilleland and Katz, 2016). The main interest of flood frequency analysis is, to estimate the discharge that, on average, is exceeded once within a given return period T (Reiss, 2007).

The traditional approach in hydrological EVA involves using annual water discharge maxima as block maxima, referred to as the BLOCK method (Reiss, 2007). This approach typically employs the generalized extreme value (GEV) distribution function to model block maxima (Gilleland, 2024). Depending on the data, the GEV distribution function reduces to one of the three types: Fréchet, Weibull or Gumbel distribution, as originally proposed by Fisher and Tippett (1928). The parameters of the GEV distribution are commonly estimated using maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) (Gilleland and Katz, 2016). The theoretical relation between the exceedance probability and the return period is given by the formula:

$$p = \frac{1}{T}, \quad (1)$$

where p is the exceedance probability of a certain value in a year and T is the return period in years (Coles, 2007). Empirical return periods, used for instance to derive observed data points in plots, are calculated directly from the data. For a sample of size n the empirical exceedance probability p_j for the j th largest observation, where $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, is defined as:

$$p_j = \frac{j - \alpha}{n + 1 - \alpha - \beta}, \quad (2)$$

with α and β being parameters that vary according to authors. In hydrological applications the Weibull plotting position has been recommended, which defines $\alpha = 0$ and $\beta = 0$ (Hobson, 2015). Then the empirical return period T_j becomes:

$$T_j = \frac{1}{p_j} = \frac{n + 1}{j} \quad (3)$$

An alternative to the BLOCK method is the Peak Over Threshold (POT) approach, where extreme values above a threshold value are selected (Pickands III, 1975). Selecting the threshold is critical, because the

results highly depend on it (Reiss, 2007). If the threshold is set too low, the assumption of asymptotic behaviour of the model is violated, and if the threshold is chosen too high, the number of exceedances becomes too small, resulting in high estimation uncertainty (Coles, 2007). The common approach is to select the lowest threshold possible such that the model still offers a satisfactory approximation (Coles, 2007). In this study, three different statistical tests were applied to identify the optimal threshold, as shown in Figure 4 for Sion for the time period 1995-2024.

Figure 4: Threshold Selection Plot for Sion, based on hourly discharge data from 1995 to 2024. The MRL plot was generated using the *extRemes* package, the threshold choice (TC) plots with POT and the threshold weight plot with *ihreshr* (Gilleland, 2024; Northrop and Attalides, 2024; Ribatet and Dutang, 2024). Data: Kauzlaric et al. (2025)

The threshold selection was conducted through graphical interpretation. The theoretical background is not addressed in this work; instead, readers are referred to textbooks (Coles, 2007; Bousquet, 2021) and R documentations of the relevant packages (Northrop and Attalides, 2024; Ribatet and Dutang, 2024). The threshold choice will be discussed here briefly for the example in Figure 4.

The Mean Residual Life (MRL) plot initially suggests an appropriate thresholds of over 700 m^3/s , as the mean excess appears to follow a linear trend beyond this point (Coles, 2007). However, such a high threshold results in too few exceedances for reliable model fitting. A more practical interpretation of the MRL plot points to a threshold between 320 and 460 m^3/s (Bocharov, 2022). The TC plots (shape and modified scale) support a choice lower than 420 m^3/s (Ribatet and Dutang, 2024), while the threshold weight plot indicates 334 m^3/s as an optimal threshold and discourages choices above 420 m^3/s (Northrop and Attalides, 2024). In line with the recommendation to select the lowest threshold that still

allows for a reasonable approximation of the tail behaviour (Coles, 2007), a threshold of $370 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ was ultimately chosen.

The discharge data was then declustered to obtain independent and identically distributed (IID) peak exceedances. Declustering was carried out by grouping together all consecutive exceedances occurring between the first and last exceedance within a sequence, treating them as a single cluster (Ribatet and Dutang, 2024). For each cluster, the maximum value was extracted and retained as an independent peak exceedance. The exceedances were then fitted to the Generalized Pareto (GP) distribution according to the Pickands–Balkema–De Haan theorem (Balkema and De Haan, 1974; Pickands III, 1975). The parameters of the GP distribution were estimated via maximum likelihood estimation (MLE).

The key difference between the two applied parametric methods – BLOCK and POT – lies in the identification of extreme events. Unlike the block maxima approach, the POT approach avoids dividing the data into blocks, which prevents the exclusion of extreme values simply because a higher value occurs within the same block (Coles, 2007). This characteristic makes POT particularly advantageous for shorter time series. However, a known limitation to the POT method is its sensitivity to the chosen threshold – analogous to the sensitivity of the BLOCK method to block size (Coles, 2007).

Once a model is fitted, the procedures for validating and interpreting EVA using either BLOCK or POT are comparable. The fit of the data to the distribution (GEV or GP) was always validated through Gumbel plots, QQ plots and density plots. An example is shown in Figure 5 for the station in Brig.

Validation Plots for Brig with all Data

Figure 5: Model validation plots for Brig using annual maximum discharge data from 1916 to 2024. Here the GEV distribution function was used, and the parameters were estimated via MLE. Discharges from 320 to 400 – corresponding to return periods of 3-10 years – appear to be underestimated by around twenty m^3/s . For higher return periods the GEV distribution provides a satisfactory fit. Data: BAFU (2025a)

In this thesis, the significance level α was set to 0.2, which translates to a 80% confidence interval (c.i.). For all subsequent plots the 80% c.i. is indicated, which represents the 10% and 90% quantiles of the MLE sampling distribution.

3.2 Data Scenarios

An initial EVA was conducted using all available annual maximum discharge values, applying the BLOCK method. This is referred to as the “All Data” scenario.

A second estimation focused on natural conditions, as introduced earlier. For this, annual maxima from 1905 to 1955 – before most dams were constructed in the Rhône catchment (Swiss Committee on Dams, 2015) – were used to calculate flood estimates for specific return period. Since several annual maxima were missing for this period at most stations (except for Porte du Scex), linear quantile regression was applied to estimate missing values, using data from Porte du Scex as a predictor (Koenker, 1999). J. Miquel (1984) also used a regression approach to estimate missing discharge data. EVA was then conducted using the BLOCK method. This scenario is referred to as “Natural”.

For the locations Brig, Visp, Sion, Branson and Porte du Scex flood estimations for the natural floods in the years 1987,1993 and 2000 were available from FOWG (2002). These reconstructions were integrated into a second estimation under natural conditions, referred to as “*Natural with Estimations*”.

A third set of analyses focused on the recent period from 1995 to 2024. Given the short duration of this time series (30 years) and the availability of hourly discharge maxima, the POT approach was applied. For consistency and comparison, EVA was also done using the BLOCK method for the same time period. These data scenarios are referred to as “*1995-2024 POT*” and “*1995-2024 BLOCK*”.

The estimated Q100 return values derived in this study are compared to existing estimates from various sources (BAFU, 2020; FOWG, 2002; Higray *et al.*, 2006), which differ in both methodology and time periods considered.

Among these, the “Hochwasserstatistik” published by BAFU (2020) provides estimates, using a methodology closely aligned with the one applied in this thesis for the “*All Data*” scenario. Both use the BLOCK approach, fit the GEV distribution function and estimate parameters via MLE. The difference exists in the c.i. and used time periods (as explicitly shown in Table 2). The BAFUs time series end in 2020 while this study extends to 2024. While this study applies an 80% c.i., BAFU uses a 95% c.i. These estimates are referred to as “*BAFU 2020*”.

Table 2: Comparison of used time periods in the “*All Data*” scenario (BAFU, 2025a) and the estimations from the BAFU (2020).

Locations	Gletsch	Reckingen	Brig	Sion	Branson	Porte	Visp
All Data	1956- 2024	1950- 2024	1916- 2024	1916- 2024	1941- 2024	1905- 2024	1974- 2024
BAFU	1956- 2020	1950- 2020	1966- 2020	1958- 2020	1958- 2020	1958- 2020	1967- 2020

FOWG realized two estimates for Q100 – one for natural conditions and one including the retentional effect of dams – referred to as “*FOWG 2002 Natural*” and “*FOWG 2002*”. The natural estimate used annual maxima before 1955. The second estimate used annual maxima after 1955 and until 2001. The fitting was conducted using Pearson III and log Pearson III distribution functions.

Other estimates originate from the CONSECRU2 report (Higray *et al.*, 2006) which followed the methodology established in the earlier CONSECRU1 report (Bérod and Consuegra, 1997) developed at HYDRAM. These values were obtained using observed annual peak discharges, fitted to the Gumbel distribution function, and included the natural flood reconstructions from FOWG (2002). These estimates were used for the dimensioning of the R3, as stated in the PA-R3 (Canton of Valais and Canton of Vaud, 2015), especially the Q100cible (top value of the 80% c.i.) was set as a goal for the

dimensioning of flood protectional infrastructures. These values will be referred to as “*CONSECRU2 observed*”.

Finally, the CONSECRU2 report included a full modelling approach. A stochastic generator for meteorological variables combined with the GSM-SOCONT (Glacier and SnowMelt – SOil COntribution model; Schaepli *et al.*, 2005) hydrological model was used to simulate discharge series. The model was calibrated using historical data and reconstructed floods (FOWG, 2002). The Gumbel distribution function was then fitted to the synthetically generated peak discharges. These estimates are referred to as “*CONSECRU2 modelled*”.

3.3 Analysis of Flood Processes

For the analysis, the discharge data from Visp, Sion, Branson and Porte du Scex was considered, along with a total of fifteen rainfall measurement stations located within their respective catchment. From the hourly discharge time series, the daily maximum discharge was extracted.

To relate discharge events to rainfall patterns, a rain index RI was constructed using Canonical-Correlation Analysis (CCA). The CCA maximizes the correlation between the discharge time series X at a location at the day i and n precipitation time series Y_1, \dots, Y_n in the catchment area (Hotelling, 1936). Y is further divided into temporally delayed time series for the days $i - k, k \in \mathbb{N}$. The CCA determined coefficients $\alpha_{1,i}, \alpha_{1,i-1}, \dots, \alpha_{1,i-k_1}, \dots, \alpha_{n,i}, \dots, \alpha_{n,i-k_n}$ such that the correlation between X and the sum

$$RI := \alpha_{1,i}Y_{1,i} + \dots + \alpha_{1,i-k_1}Y_{1,i-k_1} + \dots + \alpha_{n,i}Y_{n,i} + \dots + \alpha_{n,i-k_n}Y_{n,i-k_n}, \quad (4)$$

is maximal (Härdle and Simar, 2007). The rain index RI was defined as this linear combination for the location of the discharge time series X . The integers k_1, \dots, k_n , representing the number of lag days for each rainfall station, were determined by computing the cross-correlation between X and Y_j for $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Cross-Correlation between the daily maximum discharge of the Rhône in Sion [m^3/s] and daily rainfall measurements in Leukerbad [mm]. A lag value of $k = 1$ was selected, as the correlation is both positive and significant for the same day ($i = 0$) and for the previous day ($i = -1$). Data: Kauzlaric et al., 2025; MeteoSwiss, 2025

The objective was to ensure that the rain index was as causally aligned as possible with the peak discharge values. This meant not only maximizing the correlation through the CCA. For example in Figure 6, the coefficients for the significant negative correlations for the days $i - k, k \in \{3, \dots, 8\} \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ were set to zero. The correlation in these days could be explained through meteorology, for instance through the fact that the probability of a rainy day following another rainy day is higher than a rainy day following a day with no rain. Markov simulations of precipitation, as for instance done by Pranto *et al.* in 2024, work because of these transition probabilities. These correlations are probably not helpful to optimize the causal explanation power of the rain index.

Following the construction of the rain index, a POT analysis was applied on the index values to identify extreme precipitation events (EPEs). An EPE was defined as rainfall event with a return period of at least one year. This definition is appropriate in the context of discharge analysis, as it excludes snowfall events, which do not immediately contribute to runoff. Additionally, POT analysis was performed for the daily maximum discharge series, which resulted in independent peak discharges spanning from 1980 to 2024. The independent peak discharges could then be classified into two categories: Discharges coinciding with EPEs and discharges not associated with EPEs. Then EVA was done with including the EPEs and excluding the EPEs.

4 Results

4.1 Estimations of Return Values

The data in Table 3 indicate that the highest discharges were predominantly recorded for the year 2024. Specifically, five out of the seven stations registered the highest water levels – and corresponding peak discharges Q_{max} – in June 2024. The exceptions were Gletsch, which recorded its peak in 2013 and Porte du Scex, which peaked in 2000.

Table 3: Recorded maximal discharge Q_{max} [m^3/s] at different locations and the rank R_T of the discharge for selected years. Data: BAFU (2025a).

Location	Year of Q_{max}	Q_{max} [m^3/s]	R_{1987}	R_{1993}	R_{2000}	R_{2024}
Gletsch	2013	56	7	10	61	6
Reckingen	2024	245	2	4	12	1
Brig	2024	589	3	6	2	1
Visp (Vispa)	2024	495	3	2	4	1
Sion	2024	958	6	4	3	1
Branson	2024	1081	5	4	2	1
Porte du Scex	2000	1363	6	3	1	2

To better contextualize the severity of the 2024 flood event, Table 4 presents the estimated return periods based on the model of the “All Data” scenario.

Table 4: Estimated Return Periods for the floods of the years 2000 and 2024 for different locations along the Rhône River. Data: BAFU (2025a).

Location	$RP(2000)$	$RP(2024)$
Gletsch	1	14
Reckingen	7	120
Brig	65	83
Visp (Vispa)	12	134
Sion	88	152
Branson	65	128
Porte du Scex	729	120

The results show that the 2024 flood had return periods exceeding 120 years at five out of seven locations, highlighting the magnitude of this event. Among these, Sion exhibited the highest return period of 152 years. In contrast, Gletsch deviates from the overall pattern, showing a notably lower return period of 14 years for the event in 2024. Noticeable is the very high return period of over 700 years for the 2000 flood at Porte du Scex. The probability that two events of the magnitudes of the 2024

and the 2000 flood (or higher) would occur at Porte du Scex in the course of 25 years is $\sim 0.6\%$, under the assumption that the system is static (see details for this calculation in the second section of the appendix). Table 5 presents Q100 discharge estimates under various scenarios and for the different locations.

Table 5: Best estimations of the Q100 return values [m^3/s] rounded to the nearest multiple of five. There is no data for scenario IIb for Gletsch and Reckingen, because there are no reconstructions of natural floods at these locations (FOWG, 2002). Data: BAFU (2025a) and Kauzlaric et al. (2025).

Station/Scenario	All Data (BLOCK)	Natural (BLOCK)	Natural with est. (BLOCK)	Recent (POT)	Recent (BLOCK)
Time Period	all recordings	1905-1955	1905-1955 and 3 reconstructions	1995-2024	1995-2024
Gletsch	40	25	-	45	60
Reckingen	235	175	-	215	345
Brig	615	495	665	665	885
Visp (Vispa)	435	220	365	355	460
Sion	920	900	1130	925	1440
Branson	1045	925	1130	1165	1420
Porte du Scex	1175	1095	1440	1400	1765

The highest estimates were obtained using the “1995-2024 BLOCK” scenario. The lowest estimates resulted from the “Natural” scenario. The “Natural” estimates are on average 16% lower than the “All Data” estimates. This reduction was more pronounced in the Upper Valais, where the decrease averaged 33%, compared to only 7% in the Lower Valais. This aligns with the fact that there are more reservoirs further down the Rhône River. The “Natural with estimations” estimates – which include reconstructed floods from 1987, 1993 and 2000 from FOWG (2002) – are on average 9% higher than the “All Data” estimates. The location Visp shows an adverse trend (-19%). When neglecting Visp the change augments to 15%.

The “1995-2024 POT” yielded values, which are higher than the “All Data” estimates, except for Visp and Reckingen, which show an adverse trend. The “1995-2024 POT” estimates are similar to the “Natural with estimations” estimates for the locations Brig, Visp, Branson and Porte du Scex, having deviations bounded by $\pm 3\%$.

The “1995-2024 BLOCK” scenario yields estimates that are, on average, 41% higher than those derived from the “All Data” scenario and 37% higher than the “1995-2024 POT” estimates. A visual comparison of the BLOCK and POT estimates is provided in Figure 7. The insecurities are the highest for this BLOCK estimation, because only thirty annual maxima were used for the fit model. The POT estimates, including their 80% c.i., fall within the 80% c.i. of the BLOCK estimates (see Figure 7).

However, for the stations at Reckingen and Sion, the best estimates obtained with the BLOCK method, fall outside of the c.i. of the corresponding POT estimates.

Figure 7: Comparison of the POT and BLOCK Q100 estimates with 10% and 90% quantiles, based on data from 1995 to 2024. Data: BAFU (2025a) and Kauzlaric et al. (2025).

Several flood estimations for the Rhône River have previously been conducted (Bérod and Consuegra, 1997; FOWG, 2002; Higray *et al.*, 2006; BAFU, 2020), as discussed in section 3.2. Figure 8 provides a comparative overview of return values derived in this thesis alongside those from earlier assessments for the respective locations.

Comparison of Q100 and Q50 Return Values for Data Scenarios and Locations

Figure 8: Comparison of Q100 and Q50 return values for all locations and all data scenarios (inclusively the estimates from prior analyses). The confidence levels vary between $\alpha = 0.2$ for the five data scenarios of this thesis, $\alpha = 0.1$ for the “CONSECRU2 modelled” and $\alpha = 0.05$ for the “BAFU 2020”. Data: BAUFU (2025a), Kaulzarlic et al. (2025), FOWG (2002), Higray et al. (2006) and BAUFU (2020).

The "*CONSECRU2 modelled*" scenario produced the highest Q100 estimates for Porte du Scex. For the other six locations, the "*1995-2024 BLOCK*" scenario yielded the highest flood estimates, thereby there are no "*CONSECRU2 modelled*" estimates for Reckingen and Gletsch. The "*Natural*" scenario resulted in the lowest Q100 values for Gletsch, Reckingen, Visp and Branson. At Brig, the lowest estimate was provided by the "*CONSECRU2 modelled*" scenario, while for Sion and Porte du Scex, the lowest Q100 estimates were derived from "*BAFU 2020*" and "*FOWG 2002*", respectively.

Q100 estimates from the "*All Data*" scenario closely align (within a 5% deviation) with results from prior studies at several locations:

- "*BAFU 2020*" for Gletsch
- "*FOWG 2002 Natural*", "*BAFU 2020*" and "*CONSECRU2 observed*" (90% quantile) for Brig.
- "*CONSECRU2 observed*" (90% quantile) for Visp.
- "*FOWG 2002 Natural*" and "*FOWG 2002*" for Sion
- "*FOWG 2002*" for Branson
- "*FOWG 2002 Natural*" and "*BAFU 2020*" for Porte du Scex

Q100 estimates from the "*1995-2024 POT*" scenario closely align (within a 5% deviation) with results from prior studies at several locations:

- "*CONSECRU2 observed*" (90% quantile) for Reckingen and Brig
- "*FOWG 2002 Natural*" and "*FOWG 2002*" for Visp and Sion

Q100 estimates from the "*Natural with estimations*" closely align (within a 5% deviation) with results from prior studies at several locations:

- "*CONSECRU2 observed*" (90% quantile) for Brig.
- "*FOWG 2002*" for Visp

The "*1995-2024 POT*" Q100 estimates were all lower than the "*Natural with estimations*" estimates, on average 6%. However, the "*1995-2024 BLOCK*" Q100 estimates were all higher than the "*Natural with estimations*" estimates, on average 27%.

A more detailed comparison between "*All Data*" and "*BAFU 2020*" estimates is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Comparison of two Q100 estimates – the “All Data” estimate (green) and the “BAFU 2020” estimate (pink). Data: BAFU (2025a)

The “All Data” Q100 estimate was on average 9% higher than the Q100 estimate of the BAFU. For Gletsch (-0.7%) and Brig (-0.5%) there is no big difference. When excluding these two locations, the “All Data” estimate is on average 13% higher than the estimate of the BAFU. The c.i. from “BAFU 2020” are significantly wider, because a lower confidence level $\alpha = 0.05$ was used, and for Brig, Sion and Porte du Scex significantly fewer annual maxima were included (as discussed in section 3.2).

Another comparison is provided by examining the 90% quantile estimates of Q100 from the “All Data”, “Natural with estimations”, and “POT 1995-2024” scenarios against the Q100cible value (see Table 6). The Q100cible, defined in the CONSECRU2 report and adopted as the design target for the R3 infrastructure, serves as a critical benchmark. In Figure 8, this value is represented by the pink point labelled “Q100 top 80% c.i. ”, corresponding to the data scenario “CONSECRU2 observed” as detailed in section 3.2.

Table 6: Comparison of the Q100cible values (as described in the PA-R3 and obtained in CONSECRU2) with new 90% quantile estimates of Q100. Data: Higray et al. (2006), BAFU (2025a), Kauzlaric et al. (2025) and FOWG (2002)

Location	Q100cible [m³/s]	All Data [m³/s] (90% quantile)	Natural with est. [m³/s] (90% quantile)	1995-2024 POT [m³/s] (90% quantile)
Porte du Scex	1660	1255	1660	1845
Branson	1310	1190	1285	1580
Sion	1240	1005	1325	1175
Brig	640	730	870	930
Visp	450	635	440	525
Reckingen	205	290	-	290

The Q100cible values fall within the range of this thesis's 90% quantile estimates for Porte du Scex, Branson, Sion, and Visp. In contrast, for Brig and Reckingen, all new estimates exceed the Q100cible benchmark. The highest positive relative deviation is observed between Q100cible and “1995-2024 POT” for Brig (+45%). The highest negative relative deviation is observed between Q100cible and “All Data” for Porte du Scex (-24%).

Figure 10: Return Levels and Threat Zones (BAFU, 2025b) for the measurement station at the Rhône. Data: BAFU (2025a) and Kauzlaric et al. (2025)

In Figure 10 the obtained return levels for three data scenarios are compared to the estimated threat levels from the BAFU (2025b). Three estimates – “All Data”, “Natural with estimations” and “POT 1995-2024” – are plotted. The colouring and labelling of the threat levels is reproduced from the BAFU. Almost all Q100 values lie within the fifth (most threatful) zone. Most Q50 values lie within the fourth zone.

4.2 Analysis of Flood Processes

First, the results of the rain index constructions are presented. The complete linear combination used to define the rain index is provided in the appendix.

Visp: The cross-correlation analysis between daily discharge of the Vispa at Visp (day i) and four rainfall time series (Zermatt, Grächen, Ackersand/Stalden, and Visp) for the period 1980-2024 revealed statistically significant correlations for days i , $i - 1$ and $i - 2$. The stations Zermatt and Grächen received the highest weights in the rain index construction. The resulting correlation between the rain index and the discharge was 0,15.

Sion: Cross-correlation between the Rhône discharge and ten rainfall time series showed significant relationships for rainfall at days i , $i - 1$, and $i - 2$. However, rainfall at day $i - 2$ showed insignificant correlation for stations such as Visp, Sierre, Leukerbad, and Montana, which are geographically closer to Sion than most of the other stations. The highest weighted coefficients in the CCA were associated with rainfall at Zermatt, Grächen, and Grimentz on day $i - 1$. The correlation between the rain index and discharge at Sion was 0.16.

Branson: Cross-correlation between the discharge of the Rhône in Branson and ten precipitation measurement time series showed significant correlations between the discharge (day i) and rainfall at days i , $i - 1$, ..., $i - 5$ for the measurement stations in Grächen, Hérémence and Grimentz. As in Sion, the measured rain at Zermatt, Grächen and Grimentz at the day $i - 1$ received the highest weighted coefficients through the CCA. Low but statistically significant weights were assigned to Hérémence for days $i - 5$, $i - 4$, and $i - 3$, and to Grächen for day $i - 5$. The correlation between the rain index and the discharge is 0.16.

Porte du Scex: Cross-correlation between the discharge of the Rhône in Porte du Scex and all fifteen selected rainfall time series indicated significant correlations from days i to $i - 5$ at stations such as Grächen, Hérémence and Grimentz. Rainfall at Morgins, Gryon and Les Diablerets at the day $i - 1$ had the highest weighted coefficients in the creation of the rain index. Lower weighted but statistically significant coefficients were observed for Grächen, Visp, and Hérémence for days $i - 5$ and $i - 4$. The correlation between the rain index and discharge at this location was 0.23.

As detailed in the methodology section, the rain index is used to identify EPEs, which are then aligned with peak discharge events (as shown in Figure 11). These peak discharge events were used to fit an EVA model using the GP distribution and MLE within the POT framework.

Return Period / Return Value Plots (POT, 1980-2024) with marked EPEs

Figure 11: Return period and return value plots for Visp, Sion, Branson and Porte du Scex, calculated using the POT method. All data (red and blue points) from 1980 to 2024 was used for the calculation of the model. Red points indicate discharge events classified as EPEs. Data: Kauzlaric et al. (2025) and MeteoSwiss (2025).

The results of the analysis, as visualized in Figure 11, are the following:

Visp: Out of 93 independent peak discharge events, 6 coincided with EPEs (marked in red in Figure 11), leading to a 7% representation of EPEs. Notably, three out of the four highest observed flood events over the last 45 years were caused by EPEs. Among the ten highest discharge events, 30% coincided with EPEs.

Sion: 6 out of 63 independent peak discharge events were classified as EPEs, leading to a representation of 10%. Out of the three highest discharges two are classified as EPEs. Among the ten highest discharge events, 30% coincided with EPEs.

Branson: 14 out of 67 independent peak discharge events were classified as EPEs, leading to a representation of 21%. Out of the five highest discharges three were classified as EPEs. Among the ten highest discharge events, 50% coincided with EPEs.

Porte du Scex: 12 out of 55 independent peak discharge events were classified as EPEs, leading to a representation of 22%. Out of the three highest discharges two were classified as EPEs. Among the ten highest discharge events, 40% coincided with EPEs.

The discharges aligning with EPEs (red points in Figure 11) lie close to the upper bound of the 80% c.i.

Figure 12 contrasts the POT based return period estimation with and without EPEs for Visp. Including EPEs results in an estimated Q100 of 350 m³/s, whereas excluding them yields a lower estimate of 285 m³/s, indicating a difference of 65 m³/s.

Figure 12: Return Level Plot for the Vispa in Visp calculated with POT for the period from 1980 - 2024 with two estimation curves – with and without EPEs. Data: Data: Kauzlaric et al. (2025) and MeteoSwiss (2025).

Similar results are obtained for the other three measurement sites:

Sion: The estimation for the Q100 is 997m³/s when including all peak discharge events. It is reduced by 100m³/s when excluding the peak discharges classified as EPEs.

Branson: The Q100 estimate is 1105m³/s when including all peak discharge events. It is reduced by 130m³/s when excluding the peak discharges classified as EPEs.

Porte du Scex: The estimation for the Q100 is 1380m³/s when including all peak discharge events. It is reduced by 145m³/s when excluding the peak discharges classified as EPEs.

In general, the upper tail of the peak discharge distribution is not predominantly influenced by EPEs. However, the proportion of EPEs tends to be higher at locations with larger catchment areas, a greater number of rainfall stations within the catchment, and a stronger correlation between the rain index and discharge. The percentage of EPEs increases toward the extreme end of the discharge distribution. The significance of EPEs is further highlighted by comparing extreme value models: excluding events associated with EPEs from the fit results in systematically lower estimates of the Q100.

5 Discussion

5.1 Estimations of Return Values

The analysis of the 2024 flood event highlighted its magnitude along the Rhône River. At all sites from Reckingen to Branson, the 2024 flood ranked as the highest recorded flood since the beginning of measurements. An exception was the small catchment of Gletsch, where the 2024 event was not particularly rare or severe – not an unexpected result given that this small, high-altitude, glaciated catchment often behaves differently from the broader regional pattern. The other exception was Porte du Scex, where the 2024 event ranked second, exceeded by the 2000 event, which was particularly severe at Porte du Scex.

The impact of the 2024 flood on EVA became apparent when comparing the “*BAFU 2020*” estimates with those based on the extended “*All Data*” estimates, which includes data from 2021 to 2024. On average, the “*All Data*” estimates were 13% higher than the “*BAFU 2020*” values. However, this comparison may be biased or affected by differences in data coverage, as the “*BAFU 2020*” analysis excluded some earlier years for stations such as Brig, Sion, Branson, and Porte du Scex, which were included in the “*All Data*” scenario.

The “*POT 1995-2024*” Q100 estimates were, on average, 4% higher than the Q100 estimates derived from the “*All Data*” scenario. The “*BLOCK 1995-2024*” estimates were considerably less precise and should not be regarded as reliable. Nevertheless, these estimates were on average 41% higher than the “*All Data*” Q100 estimates, suggesting that the increase stems not only from methodological differences but also from the higher extremity of events in the time period from 1995 to 2024. The hypothesis proposed that Q100 estimates for the more recent time period exceed those derived from the entire dataset. This hypothesis can be partially accepted, as the estimates for 1995 to 2024 are higher than the “*All Data*” estimates.

There were exceptions to this trend in the Upper Valais. At Reckingen and Visp, the “*POT 1995–2024*” estimates were 9% and 18% lower, than the “*All Data*” Q100 estimates. However, the BLOCK estimates still show increases of 46% and 6%. The large increase in BLOCK estimates at Reckingen suggests that the lower POT estimate may result from an inappropriate threshold choice that underestimated extreme values. In Visp, the modest 6% increase in BLOCK estimates – well below the 41% average – may point to other contributing factors beyond threshold selection. These could include the stochastic nature of flood occurrence, where even in systems prone to extreme events, decades can pass without major floods. As the Vispa is flowing through a lateral valley of the main valley of the Valais, the stochasticity could be to some degree independent from the other sites at the Rhône. Additionally, Visp's catchment characteristics – such as higher mean altitude and greater glaciation (see Table 1) – may result in different flood dynamics compared to other sites.

The generally higher estimates for the more recent time period may reflect changes in flood hydrology associated with a warming climate (FOEN, 2021).

However, this analysis does not conclusively reveal such a trend, as flood occurrence remains largely stochastic. For example, the probability of the 2000 and 2024 flood (or higher floods) occurring within 25 years at Porte du Scex is low (0.6%), but not impossible. Still this low probability could indicate a non-static flood occurrence (as a result of a possible change in flood hydrology through climate change). The probability rises to 1.5% when calculating the return periods of the 2000 and 2024 floods with the “*POT 1995-2024*” model and rises to 31% with the “*BLOCK 1995-2024*” model, respectively. The impact of climate change on flood dynamics along the Rhône could be further investigated by examining the causes of recent extreme events and linking them to meteorological variables that have been affected by climate change.

The “*Natural*” estimates were the lowest among all scenarios, averaging 16% lower than the “*All Data*” estimates. This seems like an undesirable result, as one would expect higher discharge values under natural conditions, without the retentional effect of reservoirs. Several factors contribute to this discrepancy:

First, the period for the estimation – 1905 to 1955 – did not include any extreme flood events (like the 2000 or 2024 flood). Notably, during the 1948 flood, a dam rupture near Porte du Scex reduced the effective discharge of the Rhône (FOWG, 2002). For that year, annual maxima at Reckingen and Gletsch were estimated through regression with data from Porte du Scex. Consequently, the values for all three stations are likely underestimated.

Second, the quantile regression model used, has inherent limitations. The correlation between the discharge at Porte du Scex and the other stations was only approximately 0.7, reducing the reliability of the regression-based estimations. Additionally, the regression tends to reduce the variance of the data, which directly leads to lower estimations due to the formula of the GEV distribution function (Fisher and Tippett, 1928). For example, at Branson, the standard deviation of the annual maxima estimated via regression was $\sqrt{\sigma_{reg}} = 139$, compared to $\sqrt{\sigma_{obs}} = 147$ for the observed data.

Due to these reasons the natural conditions are likely underestimated in this scenario. A similar underestimation for the natural situation at the Rhône was already done by the FOWG (2002) as described in the CONSECRU 2 report (Higray *et al.*, 2006), where estimates under natural conditions “*FOWG 2002 Natural*” were on average 1.5% lower than “*FOWG 2002*” with reservoirs. For these estimates the underestimation of the natural conditions can’t be explained through the methodology but through the use of time periods with no extreme floods, and not including the flood reconstructions in the years 1987, 1993 and 2000 (Higray *et al.*, 2006).

Including the reconstructed floods from 1987, 1993 and 2000 (FOWG, 2002) in the scenario “*Natural with estimations*”, lead to Q100 estimates that are, on average, 26% higher than the “*Natural*” estimates. These estimates are also 9% higher than the “*All Data*” estimates. The hypothesis proposed that flood estimates under natural conditions would yield higher return values than those accounting for the effects of dams. The fact that the “*Natural with estimations*” values exceed the “*All Data*” estimates provides partial support for this hypothesis.

However, at the Visp station, an inverse pattern is observed. The Q100 estimate from the “*All Data*” scenario is 19% higher than the “*Natural with estimations*” Q100. Several factors may explain this deviation: The Vispa in Visp is located in a lateral valley and is geographically rather far away from Porte du Scex, the predictor station used in the regression model, which likely introduces greater imprecision in the estimation. Additionally, the catchment characteristics of the Vispa differ - glaciation and mean altitude (see Table 1) are the highest in this catchment (excluding Reckingen and Gletsch, for which no “*Natural with estimations*” estimates exist). These factors may explain the inverse pattern for Visp.

The Q100 estimates under the “*Natural with estimations*” scenario are, on average, 27% lower than those of the “*BLOCK 1995-2024*” scenario. This difference could be attributed to four, not mutually exclusive, explanations: First, even within the “*Natural with estimations*” scenario, the Q100 values may still be underestimated, as the same regression model – with its previously discussed characteristics – was used. This would also point to them being underestimations in the more recent time period. Second, it is possible that the retentional effect of reservoirs has only a minor or negligible impact on flood mitigation along the Rhône River. Third, the influence of the more recent period on increasing Q100 values may be stronger than any mitigating effect of reservoirs. Fourth, the higher Q100 values observed in the “*BLOCK 1995–2024*” scenario might be overestimations caused by the randomness inherent in the occurrence of extreme flood events.

The Q100cible estimates (Higray *et al.*, 2006), which were among those applied in the R3 project for the design of flood protection infrastructure (PA-R3), do not appear to represent overestimations when compared to 90% quantile estimates of Q100 (see Table 6) of this thesis. Rather, they fall between the 90% Q100 estimates from the “*All Data*”, “*Natural with estimations*”, and “*POT 1995–2024*” scenarios. For the sites at Brig and Reckingen, the Q100cible values seem more like underestimates, as they are exceeded by the estimates in all three scenarios.

5.2 Insecurities and Imprecision

The calculated Q100 are very sensitive to the used methodology. For instance, the “*POT 1995-2024*” Q100 estimates augment, on average, 37% when applying the BLOCK approach. In relation to this statement, the results of POT differ a lot depending on the threshold choice (Reiss, 2007). A continuation of the example of the threshold choice for Sion (see Figure 4), is presented to make the significance

evident for this analysis. According to the graphical testing, a threshold between 340 m³/s and 420 m³/s is reasonable, with 370 m³/s ultimately selected for this analysis. In Figure 13 the return value and return period plot is shown with two curves – one for a threshold of 340 m³/s and one for 420 m³/s. There are 214 independent exceedances above 340 m³/s and 53 above 420 m³/s. The resulting Q100 estimate is 35% higher when using the higher threshold.

Figure 13: Sensitivity of the fit model to threshold choice at Sion with data from the period 1995-2024. Data: Kauzlaric et al. (2025) and MeteoSwiss (2025).

My estimations of the upper-tail behaviour of peak exceedances and annual maxima are subject to considerable uncertainty and are particularly sensitive to extreme events, such as the floods of 2024 and 2000. This sensitivity arises primarily due to the limited length of the observed time series, which spans a maximum of 120 years at Porte du Scex (Merz and Blöschl, 2009). For the data scenarios representing natural conditions and the more recent time period, the available observational records are even shorter – 50 and 30 years, respectively – making the estimates more susceptible to the influence of rare, high-magnitude events.

Longer time series for a more robust estimation of the upper tail behaviour can be generated using simulations (Macdonald *et al.*, 2024; Higray *et al.*, 2006) or by including historical floods and paleo flood records (Stedinger and Cohn, 1986). Macdonald *et al.* (2024) used a stochastic weather generator and a rainfall-runoff model to obtain longer time series.

Inaccuracies also originate from measurements. Even under optimal conditions – such as stable channel geometry and low sediment transport – flood discharge measurements can have an uncertainty of $\pm 5\%$ (Spreafico et al., 2003). Additional errors arise from extrapolating the stage-discharge relationship at high flows, where direct measurements are rarely available. Moreover, during actual flood events, measurement infrastructure might not be able to measure the stage levels due to overtopping.

Alternative statistical methods may yield better tail estimates. Other estimators than MLE could be used, such as generalized MLE, Bayesian or L-moments (Gilleland and Katz, 2016). Other distribution functions could be applied such as an exponential distribution or a log Pearson III distribution (Gilleland, 2024).

5.3 Analysis of Flood Processes

The analysis suggests that the heavy-tailed nature of the discharge distribution is not primarily driven by EPEs. This statement is justified by the observation that, on average, 85% of the peak discharges, are not coinciding with EPEs. This is visually evident in Figure 11. It is therefore assumed that many peak discharges are instead triggered by a combination of extreme runoff generation processes – related to extreme input events, such as rainfall, snowmelt and glaciermelt – combined with unfavourable antecedent conditions, such as high saturation of the subsurface or the snowpack (Thompson, Misra and Daanen, 2011).

The analysis also showed that a lot of the highest discharge peaks were associated with EPEs. Two observations support this statement: First, the proportion of EPEs among the top ten peak discharge events is disproportionately high compared to their overall occurrence (see Table 7).

Table 7: Comparison of general presence of EPEs and ratio of EPEs in the top ten discharges. Data: Kauzlaric et al. (2025) and MeteoSwiss (2025).

	Visp (Vispa)	Sion	Branson	Porte du Scex
Overall ratio of EPEs [%]	22	21	10	6
ratio of EPEs in top ten discharges [%]	30	30	50	40

Second, removing EPEs from the input of the fit model results in a mean reduction of 8% in Q100, indicating their influence on upper-tail discharge values.

This dual behaviour aligns qualitatively with the findings of Macdonald *et al.* (2024), who observed that while runoff generation processes dominate the tail of the discharge distribution in the lower to intermediate range, the distribution of EPEs begins to govern flood peaks beyond a certain return period threshold. In their analysis of German catchments, this threshold ranged between 100 and 500 years. Due to the limited duration of the available time series in this study and no modelling approach having been used, it is not possible to identify such a threshold.

The classification of flood events in this analysis was based solely on rainfall data and thus events caused by EPEs and events not caused by EPEs were classified. The last were assumed to result from different runoff generation processes. This method could be improved by creating a more complex model, including more hydrological variables like soil saturation, snow melt, glacier melt, groundwater storage, etc. More precipitation data (for example for other time periods and for the automatic precipitation measurement stations) could be included to widen the analysis. Then multiple processes could be differentiated. By using data from automatic precipitation stations the analysis could be done on an hourly scale. By improving the spatial and temporal resolution, the correlation between the rain index and the discharge could be raised and the classification of EPEs could be more realistic.

Moreover, a modelling approach could be applied to estimate longer discharge time series through stochastic rainfall series and a rainfall-runoff model. Modelling approaches are common in EVA and were for instance applied by Macdonald *et al.* (2024) or Higray *et al.* (2006). Such an approach would allow finding a return period threshold, above which the EPEs become dominant.

In this analysis, EPEs were defined as events, which would exceed a rain index with a return period of one year ($T_{EPE} = 1$). This definition could be adapted, which would lead to different results, as demonstrated in Table 8 for Porte du Scex.

Table 8: Impact of EPE definition and coinciding top discharge events at Porte du Scex. Q_{peak} are the 55 independent peak discharges of the Rhône River at Porte du Scex. Data: Kauzlaric *et al.* (2025) and MeteoSwiss (2025).

T_{EPE}	EPEs in Q_{peak}	Q100 [m^3/s]	Q100 (excluding EPEs) [m^3/s]	EPEs in top ten Q_{peak}
1	12	1380	1230	4
2	9	1380	1195	3
5	3	1380	1225	2
10	1	1380	1225	1

The definition of the rain index can be criticized as well. When looking at the discharge on day i , rain measurements back to day $i - 5$ were considered for calculating the rain index. This resulted in a specific definition of an EPE depending on the rain of multiple days. The results would have been altered when only using rain measurements from days $i - 1$ and i (as explicitly shown in Table 9 for Porte du Scex). When only considering the rain on day i the correlation of the discharge with the rain index was significantly lower. When only considering days i and $i - 1$ more EPEs were coinciding with the peak discharges.

Table 9: Impact of the temporal window on the rain index and results of the flood process analysis for Porte du Scex. Data: Kauzlaric et al. (2025) and MeteoSwiss (2025).

Considered days	$cor(RI, Q)$	EPEs in Q_{peak}	Q100 [m ³ /s]	Q100 (excluding EPEs) [m ³ /s]	EPEs in top ten Q_{peak}
i	0.13	3	1380	1245	1
$i, i - 1$	0.22	18	1380	1170	6
$i, i - 1, \dots, i - 5$	0.23	12	1380	1230	4

Despite the methodological insecurities and inconveniences, the results seem plausible and qualitatively consistent with the findings of Macdonald *et al.* (2024).

6 Conclusion and Outlook

This bachelor's thesis reassessed the flood discharges of the Rhône River through an Extreme Value Analysis (EVA) using updated datasets and various scenarios. The goal was to re-estimate the discharge values for T-year return periods and compare them with existing analyses, some used for the dimensioning of the 3rd Rhône Correction (R3). The results partially support the initial hypothesis that Q100 estimates for the more recent period and those under natural conditions are higher than those based on the full dataset, offering a new perspective on flood risk along the Rhône River in the cantons of Valais and Vaud.

An increase of extreme discharges in the more recent period (1995–2024) is evident. This suggests that the flood dynamics of the Rhône may be changing, which is consistent with the expected impacts of climate change (FOEN, 2021). The flood event of June 2024, in particular, had a significant impact on the results, leading to markedly higher Q100 estimates in most scenarios that included this event.

The analysis highlighted that the estimates for the Q100 under natural conditions, when historical flood reconstructions are included, tend to be higher than those based on the entire available data series. This supports the hypothesis, that the discharge would be greater without the retentional effect of the reservoirs. However, these Q100 estimates under natural conditions were lower than those determined for the more recent time period with the BLOCK approach. Thus, these new flood estimates for natural conditions would still underestimate floods in the more recent period from 1995 to 2024.

A key finding is that the target design values (Q100cible) used for the R3 (Etat du Valais and Etat de Vaud, 2015) do not appear to be oversized in light of the new calculations. At the locations Brig and Reckingen, the current results even suggest a possible underestimation of the risk. This work underscores the necessity of a robust flood protection project like the R3, especially because of projected settlement growth in the Rhône valley (Perlik *et al.*, 2008), which further increases damage exposure.

Furthermore, the analysis of flood processes revealed that while the distribution of extreme discharges is shaped by a combination of different runoff processes, the highest observed peak discharges disproportionately coincide with extreme precipitation events (EPEs). This has consequences for risk management: while a broad spectrum of processes is relevant for more frequent floods, EPEs must be regarded as an important driving force for the rarest and most catastrophic events.

During the course of this work, further research necessity has emerged. The greatest uncertainty in the results presented here lies in the relatively short length of the observation series. To obtain more robust estimates for rare events, other estimates would benefit from the use of stochastic weather generators in combination with rainfall-runoff models, similar to those used in the CONSECRU2 report or by Macdonald *et al.* (2024). This would allow for the generation of long, synthetic discharge time series, enabling a more precise EVA.

Furthermore, the process analysis could be deepened. By including additional hydrological and meteorological data (e.g. snow cover, soil moisture, higher-resolution precipitation data) and integrating them into a more detailed model, it would be possible to differentiate more precisely under which conditions certain processes become dominant. This would allow for the identification of thresholds at which EPEs begin to fully control flood generation.

Data and Code Accessibility

The following R-packages were used for the following causes:

- “bfsMaps” (Signorell and Guggenbühl, 2023) was used for creating the map (Figure 3)
- “extRemes” (Gilleland, 2024) was used for fitting EVA distribution functions (GEV, GP) to the data and calculating return periods and return values. Additionally, it was used for creating MRL-plots.
- “ggplot2” (Wickham *et al.*, 2007) was used for plotting some of the figures.
- “pls” (Liland, Mevik and Wehrens, 1999) for the CCA.
- “POT” (Dutang and Ribatet, 2005) for generating tc-plots and declustering data when performing POT analysis.
- “quantreg” (Koenker, 1999) was used for doing a linear, quantile regression.
- “sf” (Pebesma, 2016) was used for doing the coordinate transformations for the map (Figure 3)
- “threshr” (Northrop and Attalides, 2024) was used for generating threshold weight plots.

The following data was used:

- Annual Discharge Maxima for the measurement stations in Gletsch, Reckingen, Brig, Sion, Branson and Porte du Scex (BAFU, 2025a)
- Reconstructions of the floods in 1987, 1993 and 2000 under a natural situation (FOWG, 2002)
- Hourly Discharge for the measurement stations Gletsch, Reckingen, Brig, Visp, Sion, Branson and Porte du Scex (Kauzlaric *et al.*, 2025)
- Manual Rainfall Data for the measurement stations in Ackersand (AST), Bourg-St.-Pierre (BSP), Finhaut (CTA), Les Diablerets (DIB), Grächen (GRC), Grimentz (GRI), Gryon (GRY), Hérémente (HER), Leukerbad (LEU), Morgins (MGI), Montana (MVE), Sion (SIO), Sierre (SRE), Visp (VIS) and Zermatt (ZER) (MeteoSwiss, 2025)

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A Appendix

A.1 Rain Index Construction

Visp:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{rain_index_Visp} := & \\
 & 0.015214785 * \text{rain}\$AST[i - 2] + \\
 & 0.073718539 * \text{rain}\$AST[i - 1] + \\
 & 0.077418398 * \text{rain}\$AST[i] + \\
 & 0.043897876 * \text{rain}\$VIS[i - 1] + \\
 & 0.046306025 * \text{rain}\$VIS[i] + \\
 & 0.032814243 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 2] + \\
 & 0.102734600 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 1] + \\
 & 0.097388208 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i] + \\
 & 0.030534962 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i - 2] + \\
 & 0.105333765 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i - 1] + \\
 & 0.099371001 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i]
 \end{aligned}$$

Sion:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{rain_index_Sion} := & \\
 & 0.11515371 * \text{rain}\$AST[i - 2] + \\
 & 0.22624821 * \text{rain}\$AST[i - 1] + \\
 & 0.16947148 * \text{rain}\$AST[i] + \\
 & 0.14874627 * \text{rain}\$VIS[i - 1] + \\
 & 0.08868061 * \text{rain}\$VIS[i] + \\
 & 0.16655269 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 2] + \\
 & 0.29125830 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 1] + \\
 & 0.21531564 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i] +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0.17651179 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i - 2] + \\
&0.30696329 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i - 1] + \\
&\quad 0.23451478 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i] + \\
&0.09587300 * \text{rain}\$HER[i - 2] + \\
&0.20523538 * \text{rain}\$HER[i - 1] + \\
&\quad 0.15058642 * \text{rain}\$HER[i] + \\
&0.12915655 * \text{rain}\$SRE[i - 1] + \\
&\quad 0.08045168 * \text{rain}\$SRE[i] + \\
&0.06915759 * \text{rain}\$SIO[i - 2] + \\
&0.15268797 * \text{rain}\$SIO[i - 1] + \\
&\quad 0.10523791 * \text{rain}\$SIO[i] + \\
&0.16556669 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 2] + \\
&0.28754860 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 1] + \\
&\quad 0.23380645 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i] + \\
&0.16588104 * \text{rain}\$LEU[i - 1] + \\
&\quad 0.11042163 * \text{rain}\$LEU[i] + \\
&0.12663661 * \text{rain}\$MVE[i - 1] + \\
&\quad 0.07909267 * \text{rain}\$MVE[i]
\end{aligned}$$

Branson:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{rain_index_Branson} := \\
&0.141307289 * \text{rain}\$AST[i] + \\
&0.215994752 * \text{rain}\$AST[i - 1] + \\
&0.107468149 * \text{rain}\$AST[i - 2] + \\
&0.039459641 * \text{rain}\$AST[i - 3] + \\
&\quad 0.076014383 * \text{rain}\$VIS[i] + \\
&0.153094932 * \text{rain}\$VIS[i - 1] +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &0.048916892 * \text{rain}\$VIS[i - 2] + \\ &0.177662532 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i] + \\ &0.273068497 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 1] + \\ &0.153449636 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 2] + \\ &0.071749808 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 3] + \\ &0.041041237 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 4] + \\ &0.028171291 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 5] + \\ &0.191989525 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i] + \\ &0.284705864 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i - 1] + \\ &0.160984347 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i - 2] + \\ &0.129715265 * \text{rain}\$HER[i] + \\ &0.207877344 * \text{rain}\$HER[i - 1] + \\ &0.096557195 * \text{rain}\$HER[i - 2] + \\ &0.025491612 * \text{rain}\$HER[i - 3] + \\ &0.010226030 * \text{rain}\$HER[i - 4] + \\ &0.005890476 * \text{rain}\$HER[i - 5] + \\ &0.071213340 * \text{rain}\$SRE[i] + \\ &0.140495426 * \text{rain}\$SRE[i - 1] + \\ &0.045604994 * \text{rain}\$SRE[i - 2] + \\ &0.092764371 * \text{rain}\$SIO[i] + \\ &0.156680478 * \text{rain}\$SIO[i - 1] + \\ &0.070151391 * \text{rain}\$SIO[i - 2] + \\ &0.198356457 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i] + \\ &0.274449309 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 1] + \\ &0.152993071 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 2] + \\ &0.077855220 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 3] + \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&0.059666714 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 4] + \\
&0.052377483 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 5] + \\
&0.101373858 * \text{rain}\$LEU[i] + \\
&0.182573190 * \text{rain}\$LEU[i - 1] + \\
&0.039989490 * \text{rain}\$LEU[i - 2] + \\
&0.074208596 * \text{rain}\$MVE[i] + \\
&0.142839706 * \text{rain}\$MVE[i - 1]
\end{aligned}$$

Porte du Scex:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{rain_index_Porte} := \\
&0.08433644 * \text{rain}\$AST[i] + \\
&0.13724010 * \text{rain}\$AST[i - 1] + \\
&0.08001459 * \text{rain}\$AST[i - 2] + \\
&0.03676036 * \text{rain}\$AST[i - 3] + \\
&0.06082011 * \text{rain}\$VIS[i] + \\
&0.11824730 * \text{rain}\$VIS[i - 1] + \\
&0.05875731 * \text{rain}\$VIS[i - 2] + \\
&0.10298783 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i] + \\
&0.16643631 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 1] + \\
&0.10368658 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 2] + \\
&0.05335187 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 3] + \\
&0.03374627 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 4] + \\
&0.02583185 * \text{rain}\$GRC[i - 5] + \\
&0.11025953 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i] + \\
&0.17227152 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i - 1] + \\
&0.10858358 * \text{rain}\$ZER[i - 2] + \\
&0.09525842 * \text{rain}\$HER[i] +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &0.15696286 * \text{rain}\$HER[i - 1] + \\ &0.08835161 * \text{rain}\$HER[i - 2] + \\ &0.03956239 * \text{rain}\$HER[i - 3] + \\ &\quad 0.06390220 * \text{rain}\$SRE[i] + \\ &0.12046077 * \text{rain}\$SRE[i - 1] + \\ &0.06169057 * \text{rain}\$SRE[i - 2] + \\ &\quad 0.07322216 * \text{rain}\$SIO[i] + \\ &0.12501109 * \text{rain}\$SIO[i - 1] + \\ &0.06974772 * \text{rain}\$SIO[i - 2] + \\ &0.03160819 * \text{rain}\$SIO[i - 3] + \\ &\quad 0.12408391 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i] + \\ &0.18356124 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 1] + \\ &0.11255055 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 2] + \\ &0.06157735 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 3] + \\ &0.04710674 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 4] + \\ &0.04056370 * \text{rain}\$GRI[i - 5] + \\ &\quad 0.09624286 * \text{rain}\$LEU[i] + \\ &0.16924757 * \text{rain}\$LEU[i - 1] + \\ &0.08004387 * \text{rain}\$LEU[i - 2] + \\ &\quad 0.07749324 * \text{rain}\$MVE[i] + \\ &0.13757129 * \text{rain}\$MVE[i - 1] + \\ &0.06575476 * \text{rain}\$MVE[i - 2] + \\ &\quad 0.12395541 * \text{rain}\$BSP[i] + \\ &0.19417745 * \text{rain}\$BSP[i - 1] + \\ &0.11461572 * \text{rain}\$BSP[i - 2] + \\ &0.05203268 * \text{rain}\$BSP[i - 3] + \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 0.11369181 * \text{rain}\$CTA[i] + \\
& 0.20315028 * \text{rain}\$CTA[i - 1] + \\
& 0.10526360 * \text{rain}\$CTA[i - 2] + \\
& 0.03828461 * \text{rain}\$CTA[i - 3] + \\
& 0.15439192 * \text{rain}\$DIB[i] + \\
& 0.23025998 * \text{rain}\$DIB[i - 1] + \\
& 0.12441313 * \text{rain}\$DIB[i - 2] + \\
& 0.05443764 * \text{rain}\$DIB[i - 3] + \\
& 0.15751688 * \text{rain}\$GRY[i] + \\
& 0.22722492 * \text{rain}\$GRY[i - 1] + \\
& 0.12544294 * \text{rain}\$GRY[i - 2] + \\
& 0.06039873 * \text{rain}\$GRY[i - 3] + \\
& 0.03897809 * \text{rain}\$GRY[i - 4] + \\
& 0.16596756 * \text{rain}\$MGI[i] + \\
& 0.26154942 * \text{rain}\$MGI[i - 1] + \\
& 0.14249212 * \text{rain}\$MGI[i - 2] + \\
& 0.06533765 * \text{rain}\$MGI[i - 3]
\end{aligned}$$

A.2 Probability Calculation

Here the solution method for calculating the probability of two events, the size of the 2000 and 2024 event (or higher events), occurring within 25 years at Porte du Scex, is shown.

$$\text{“All Data” return periods: } p_{2000} = \frac{1}{729} \text{ and } p_{2024} = \frac{1}{120}$$

$$\text{“1995-2024 POT” return periods: } p_{2000} = \frac{1}{214} \text{ and } p_{2024} = \frac{1}{170}$$

$$\text{“1995-2024 BLOCK” return periods: } p_{2000} = \frac{1}{38} \text{ and } p_{2024} = \frac{1}{25}$$

$$p = (1 - (1 - p_{2000})^{25}) * (1 - (1 - p_{2024})^{25})$$

Results:

$$p_{All\ Data} \approx 0.006$$

$$p_{1995-2024 POT} \approx 0.015$$

$$p_{1995-2024 BLOCK} \approx 0.305$$

A.3 Return Values

All return values have units [m³/s]. For every return value, 3 quantiles are provided: the lower and upper bounds of the 80% c.i. (10% and 90% quantile of the sampling distribution) and the best estimation (maximum likelihood estimate MLE) (Gilleland and Katz, 2016). For the POT estimates the chosen threshold is provided. All locations are rounded to the nearest multiple of 5, except for Gletsch, which is rounded to integers.

Data: Kauzlaric *et al.* (2025), BAFU (2025a) and FOWG (2002)

“All Data”	Gletsch	Reckingen	Brig	Visp	Sion	Branson	Porte du Scex
10% - Q50	30	165	445	215	800	835	1040
MLE - Q50	35	200	525	330	860	940	1100
90% - Q50	40	240	600	445	920	1045	1165
10% - Q100	35	180	495	240	840	895	1095
MLE - Q100	40	235	615	435	920	1045	1175
90% - Q100	50	290	730	635	1005	1190	1255
10% - Q1000	45	220	665	200	945	1075	1235
MLE - Q1000	60	380	1045	1185	1115	1440	1390
90% - Q1000	80	545	1420	2165	1285	1810	1545

“Natural”	Gletsch	Reckingen	Brig	Visp	Sion	Branson	Porte du Scex
10% - Q50	25	160	370	205	775	830	995
MLE - Q50	26	170	440	215	845	890	1055
90% - Q50	27	180	515	225	920	945	1165
10% - Q100	25	160	390	205	800	850	1020
MLE - Q100	26	175	495	220	900	925	1095
90% - Q100	27	190	600	235	995	1000	1235

“Natural with estimations”	Brig	Visp	Sion	Branson	Porte du Scex
10% - Q50	425	270	880	930	1160
MLE - Q50	555	320	1015	1045	1315
90% - Q50	685	370	1150	1160	1470

10% - Q100	465	295	935	975	1230
MLE - Q100	665	365	1130	1130	1440
90% - Q100	870	440	1325	1285	1655

<i>“1995-2024 POT”</i>	Gletsch	Reckingen	Brig	Visp	Sion	Branson	Porte du Scex
Thresh.-choice	17	55	190	90	370	430	525
10% - Q50	28	125	360	170	620	690	865
MLE - Q50	35	170	495	255	760	910	1100
90% - Q50	41	215	625	340	895	1125	1335
10% - Q100	31	140	405	185	680	745	955
MLE - Q100	43	215	665	355	925	1165	1400
90% - Q100	55	290	930	525	1175	1580	1845

<i>“1995-2024 BLOCK”</i>	Gletsch	Reckingen	Brig	Visp	Sion	Branson	Porte du Scex
10% - Q50	34	145	405	170	615	740	925
MLE - Q50	50	270	710	340	1145	1165	1460
90% - Q50	66	395	1010	515	1675	1585	1995
10% - Q100	35	140	390	160	540	735	905
MLE - Q100	60	345	885	460	1440	1420	1765
90% - Q100	86	550	1385	760	2345	2105	2620

<i>1980-2024 POT (with EPEs)</i>	Visp	Sion	Branson	Porte du Scex
Thresh.-choice	80	410	440	580
10% - Q50	205	725	795	1000
MLE - Q50	270	875	960	1215
90% - Q50	340	1020	1130	1435
10% - Q100	235	765	845	1045
MLE - Q100	350	995	1105	1380
90% - Q100	465	1225	1365	1720

<i>1980-2024 POT (without EPEs)</i>	Visp	Sion	Branson	Porte du Scex
Thresh.-choice	80	410	440	580
10% - Q50	185	680	735	885
MLE - Q50	230	800	870	1055
90% - Q50	280	925	1005	1225
10% - Q100	205	715	775	915
MLE - Q100	285	900	980	1185
90% - Q100	360	1080	1180	1455